

THE ROLE OF EDUCATION TECHNOLOGIES IN ENGLISH TEACHING

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Abstract. *Learning foreign languages has been a vital need and necessity for every nation since ancient times. Language is the messenger of all innovations, discoveries and cultures. Language is becoming one of the factors that contribute to development, one of the factors that bring scientific-technical and cultural achievements. Out of more than 5,000 languages in the world, English is the third most spoken language in the world (after Spanish and Mandarin Chinese). It is the main language of the European Union, and 900 million people use it as their L1.*

Key words: *English language, pedagogical technology, teaching methods, communication.*

РОЛЬ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. *Изучение иностранных языков было жизненной необходимостью и необходимостью для каждого народа с древних времен. Язык является посланником всех инноваций, открытий и культур. Язык становится одним из факторов, способствующих развитию, одним из факторов, приносящих научно-технические и культурные достижения. Из более чем 5000 языков мира английский является третьим по распространенности языком в мире (после испанского и китайского). Это основной язык Европейского Союза, и 900 миллионов человек используют его в качестве L1.*

Ключевые слова: *английский язык, педагогическая технология, методы обучения, общение.*

In world practice, the formation of speech competence in foreign languages in the development of the professional competence (ability) of students in foreign languages, the modernization of innovative activities related to the use of modern pedagogical technologies, the gradual formation of speech etiquette competencies with a differential approach to oral speech, education Issues such as improving the efficiency of education, creating electronic educational tools and textbooks for educational subjects, expanding the possibility of using modern information and communication technologies in education are of particular importance. This, in turn, is the main factor in the deep assimilation of the knowledge of students and young people in these subjects, and it increases the quality and efficiency of education. Thanks to the large-scale reforms implemented in the education system in our country, incomparable opportunities have been created for the modern generation to acquire modern knowledge and reach perfection. Today, due to the fact that Uzbekistan is steadily progressing on the path of building a democratic legal state and a just civil society, the personnel training system has been radically reformed, and the priority of individual interest and education has been decided in the state social policy.

In today's conditions, it is appropriate to train highly qualified personnel based on modern systems and modern pedagogical technologies. The positive feature of advanced, modern pedagogical technologies is that the educational process that guarantees the achievement of the set

goals is planned and implemented effectively. In fact, 80% of the successful organization of lessons depends on the correct design, organization and implementation of the educational process.

English is a very beautiful and versatile language, it has a wonderful literature. The English language was created by scientists, philosophers and lawyers. It is not a spoken language, but a written language, that is, a language that is read, not spoken. Its aesthetic effect is complex, not childishly simple. Concepts and expressions translated from Greek and Latin are very common and widely used in English. Ancient words are beautiful, they sound pleasant to the ear, they are in harmony with the music, and they easily fall into tune. Is English a difficult language to learn? The question arises. We can answer this question, yes, in the beginning. Because it is difficult to master the English language without mastering the basic information and basic concepts of the language and connecting them with each other. After the foundation is well built, it is easy to get oil. What is the easiest, fastest and best way to learn a language? The answer to the question has been sought for many years. Currently, many higher educational institutions in the world are busy clarifying this issue. There is no correct and precise answer to this question in general, but there is a quick and easy teaching method for a specific educational group. In this regard, famous figures of world science, researchers-scientists have been confused for several years and clarified the problem by expressing their opinions and recommendations in this regard. After that, the world's only organization for language learning, teaching and assessment was created.

“Recommendations of Pan-European cooperation on language learning, teaching and assessment” were created in accordance with the order of the European Union and are intended to be applied to the process of learning and teaching all languages. The recommendations serve as a basis for creating curricula, educational standards, training manuals, and organizing and conducting tests. This document provides instructions on what knowledge, skills and abilities should be acquired in order to be able to use language as a means of communication. English language education in educational institutions is intended for practical, general educational, educational and developmental purposes. The introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies in the educational system of the Republic of Uzbekistan further enriches the content of the personnel training process in our country's educational institutions, bringing it into harmony with world standards, and at the same time, the ideology of independence, Uzbek folk pedagogy and national an became the basis for the creation of a pedagogical technology specific and suitable for mothers. Learning foreign languages has become a necessity at the moment.

Changes in the socio-economic spheres of our country, rapid development require the application of new pedagogical technologies in the educational process, the demand for finding modern methods of language teaching and applying them to the educational process has increased. Modern pedagogical technologies, methods and methods of foreign language teaching were searched for by leading scientists and methodologists. Recently, the design method and other methods have entered the teaching of English, unlike the traditional teaching method.

The design method is the organization of teaching, and students get knowledge in the form of a project through the planning process and performing practical tasks.

Another modern technology used in English classes is **collaborative technology**. In this technology, based on the cooperative pedagogy, which represents the relationship between the teacher and the student, joint education of students is carried out.

Didactic game technologies are used in the educational process in the form of a didactic game lesson. Didactic game lessons are divided into plot-role games, creative games, businessmen's games, conferences and game exercises according to the content and essence of the students' learning. The didactic purpose of each didactic game lesson, its characteristics, its place in the educational process, its content can be developed and put into practice.

Pedagogical innovation means introducing innovations and positive changes to the educational process in order to achieve an effective result.

Pedagogical innovations are created in scientific schools, educational practice and as a result of creative activity of scientists and pedagogues. Innovation is a new educational practice that is *thoroughly planned, purposefully introduced into the educational process, that is, a new procedure, a new method, methodology, technology, etc.* The specific features of innovation are as follows:

- Innovation always includes a new solution to an actual problem.
- Their use allows obtaining new qualitative results.
- Implementation of innovations leads to qualitative changes of all components in the system.

There are a number of advantages of working with interactive methods, which can be explained as follows:

1. Learners study knowledge with interest and enthusiasm. This leads to their activation.
2. Activity in the course of the lesson helps to form creative skills aimed at solving problems arising in the activities related to learning.
3. Creates an individual approach to students.

It is known that such an approach creates an opportunity to choose effective methods and ways of organizing work in the audience and outside the audience, taking into account the unique qualities of a person's character (ability, interest, memory, level of knowledge).

4. The methods of working in pairs and groups are widely used in the educational process. This will help learners to develop skills such as responsibility, teamwork, and creativity.

5. Independent work skills are formed in learners. They do not receive their knowledge ready-made, but due to their activeness in the process of learning, they learn to master and think creatively through independent analysis of the acquired knowledge. Also, because they are taught to work with different literature, they develop independent reading and research skills.

6. Learners are strongly motivated to learn.

7. Creates a need to use the studied foreign language in speech communication and creates a desire for students to communicate.

8. Learners' confidence in their abilities increases, they are given the opportunity to overcome psychological obstacles such as fear of making mistakes and panic.

9. It helps to form skills and abilities to independently read and learn outside of class and to express critical opinions in relation to the opinions expressed, to be able to prove one's views in them.

The following conclusions can be drawn from the above-mentioned points. The use of modern pedagogical technologies in English language classes is undoubtedly effective in English language education and its popularization.

note the great efforts being made by the Uzbekistan's government to mitigate

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